

5. Formaldehyde increases the tensile strength of the fibre specially in slightly alkaline solution. It also prevents the bacterial decomposition of both raw and delignified fibre.

6. Removal of lignin makes the fibre more susceptible to bacterial action.

I wish to record here my sincere and grateful thanks to my teacher Dr. J. K. Chowdhury, Ph.D., for designing the apparatus and many valuable suggestions, and to Prof. Dr. J. C. Ghosh for offering me all facilities for work.

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Vitamin C in Indian Food-stuffs.

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Since the identification of vitamin C (ascorbic acid) with "Hexuronic acid" additional interest has naturally been aroused in obtaining further information about it. The reducing property of ascorbic acid has been taken advantage of for the determination of the ascorbic acid content of different materials, both of vegetable and animal origins. The Tillmans technique of titration with the oxidation-reduction indicator, 2:6-dichlorophenol-indophenol, has been modified by Harris and Ray (*Biochem. J.*, 1933, 27, 303) and Birch, Harris and Ray (*ibid.*, 1933, 27, 590) and they claim that in general the figures obtained by the chemical method agree with those obtained by the biological technique of assay.

The present paper records certain results obtained by the titration technique with the extracts of some Indian food-stuffs and it will be observed that some of the fruits investigated have a very high reducing power. The vitamin C content of germinated and ungerminated *mung* (*Phaseolus mungo*) has been investigated by both the chemical and biological methods.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Titration with 2:6-dichlorophenol-indophenol.—Essentially the method of Harris and Ray (*loc. cit.*), and Birch, Harris and Ray

(*loc. cit.*) was followed. It has already been reported (Guha and Ghosh, *Current Science*, 1934, 2, 390) that the dye is decolorised by itself in the presence of trichloroacetic acid. The velocity of reduction by ascorbic acid is, however, so rapid that in most cases this spontaneous decolorisation by trichloroacetic acid introduces no perceptible error. In the cases of trichloroacetic acid extracts containing very small amounts of ascorbic acid, however, where the time taken for titration exceeds 1-2 minutes, an appreciable error may be introduced. We have, therefore, in all our estimates added 1 c.c. of glacial acetic acid to 0.05 c.c. of 0.01M-dye in order to inhibit the spontaneous decolorisation, before titration against the trichloroacetic acid extracts (Guha and Ghosh, *loc. cit.*). We have lately found that Bessey and King (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1933, 103, 687) have used hot acetic acid extracts in many cases with the same purpose. We had ourselves tried extraction with cold glacial acetic acid but the centrifugate was opalescent and the extraction not so satisfactory as with trichloroacetic acid. After the end of titration, a faint pink colour persists very frequently, but with a little experience any error from this source may be obviated.

Titration with iodine.—Titrations of the trichloroacetic acid extracts have also been carried out with 0.01N-iodine. The results obtained by this method are, as might be expected, at variance with those obtained by titration with the indophenol indicator. The two values agree, however, for lemon juice, as has already been pointed out by Bessey and King (*loc. cit.*). In lemon juice, therefore, the amount of reducing substances other than the one reacting specifically with the indophenol indicator must be small.

In Table I are given the titration values of trichloroacetic acid extracts of the food-stuffs with 0.01 N-iodine and 0.01M-2:6-dichlorophenol-indophenol. The values of ascorbic acid have been estimated on the assumption that the sole reducing substance of the extracts, reacting with either reagent, is ascorbic acid. Two series of values have thus been obtained, and as will be seen, the only agreement is in the case of lemon juice (Bessey and King, *loc. cit.*). This is as might be expected, as usually there are reducing substances present, which react with iodine but not with the dye under our conditions of titration. The figures for ascorbic acid, given in the last column and computed on the assumption of the relative specificity of the method of titration with the indophenol dye are, therefore, held to be more reliable. There is substantial

(Harris and Ray, *Biochem. J.*, 1933, 27, 580) but not conclusive, evidence for this view.

1 c.c. of the dye solution and 1 c.c. of the iodine solution were equivalent to 1.04 mg. and 0.88 mg. of ascorbic acid respectively.

The food-stuffs investigated are all fruits, except No. 8, 11, 17, 18, 22 and 26, which are vegetables and No. 15, which is a pulse. In Table II the ascorbic acid values of the richest Indian fruits are given.

*The Vitamin C Values of Germinated and Ungerminated
Kanchamung (Phaseolus mungo).*

Kanchamung was germinated by being soaked with water for 48 hours covered with a piece of moist muslin in a procelain dish.

FIG. 1.

Curves obtained on administering 4 g. germinated mung daily. No scorbutic symptoms noticed during a 63 day expt. period.

The vitamin C values of germinated and ungerminated *mung* were estimated by both the biological and titration methods. The biological tests were carried out by the protective technique. Guinea-pigs, weighing about 300 g., were fed on a basal diet, consisting of 70 part oats, 20 parts crushed gram, 10 parts bran and 1 part cod-liver oil. A block of rock salt was also provided in each case. Those receiving this diet alone rapidly declined in weight and died within 2-3 weeks with typical scorbutic symptoms. The potency of the *mung* was tested by observing whether protection would be afforded for a 63-day period by graded doses of the food-stuff.

FIG. 2.

The curves obtained on administering 12 g. ungerminated *mung* daily. All the animals succumbed within 4 weeks.

and ungerminated *mung*. (As, however, the germinated and ungerminated *mung* contain 65.4 and 8.4% water respectively, there is about 7.8 times increase in vitamin C produced by germination, calculated on the basis of dry weight). Johnson (*Biochem. J.*, 1933, 27, 1942) states that germinated peas contain a substance in addition to ascorbic acid, which reduces the indophenol reagent and that trichloroacetic acid does not extract all of the ascorbic acid of germinated peas. In our experiments also the titrimetric value of the trichloroacetic acid extract does not appear to agree well with the high biological value of the fresh germinated *mung*. Its protective dose is 4 g., whereas titrimetrically only 0.16 mg. ascorbic acid appears to be present in the trichloroacetic acid extract of this quantity of germinated *mung*.

Figs. 1 and 2 show that 4 g. of germinated *mung* daily are able to afford protection (cf. Wata and Eyles, *Indian J. Med. Res.*, 1932, 20, 89) but even 12 g. of ungerminated *mung* daily are quite ineffective. 3 G. of germinated *mung* were found to be just insufficient to prevent scurvy. This would show that, calculated on the basis of fresh weight, more than 4 times ascorbic acid is produced in *mung* by germination, as determined biologically. It will, however, be seen from Table I (serial No. 15) that on the basis of fresh weights, the ascorbic acid content, as estimated by titration with the indophenol indicator, is 0.04 mg. per g. in both the germinated

TABLE I.

Serial No.	Bengali names:	English names.	Scientific names.	Values per g. of fresh food stuff.			
				I ₂ -values (0.01 N).	Ascorbic acid(?) as calculated from iodine values.	Indicator (0.01 M).	Ascorbic acid as calculated from dye values.
1	(i) Am. (Bengali deshi variety)* (Kanche).	Mango (green)	Mangifera indica	0.83 c.c.	0.79 mg.	0.2 c.c.	0.29 mg.
	(ii) " (Bengali deshi variety)* (Paka)	(ripe)	"	0.18	0.16	0.1	0.10
	(iii) " Fozli variety (ripe)	(ripe)	"	0.5	0.44	0.88	0.34
	(iv) " Langra variety (ripe)	(ripe)	"	1.0	0.88	0.66	0.69
	(v) " (Bengali deshi variety)@ (a) Mukul	(bud)	"	0.41	0.36	0.099	0.10
	(b) Kanche	(green)	"	0.11	0.097	0.051	0.05
	(c) Paka	(ripe)	"	0.05	0.044	0.02	0.02
2	Anarash (Bengali deshi variety)	Pine-apple	Ananas sativa	0.31	0.27	0.21	0.22
	" (Singapore)	"	"	0.26	0.29	0.07	0.07
	" Canned (Malay)	"	"	0.14	0.12	0.099	0.11
3	Begoon (Blue variety)		Solenum melongena	0.09	0.079	0.05	0.05
	" (White variety)		"	0.12	0.11	0.05	0.05
4	Bel (Paka)	Wood-apple	Aegle marmelos	0.98	0.89	0.17	0.18
5	Dahim	Pomegranate	Punica granatum	0.20	0.18	0.11	0.11
6			Cucumis melo	0.08	0.063	0.03	0.03
7	Golap-jam	Rose-apple	Eugenia jambos	0.14	0.12	0.06	0.06
8	Hinche		Eubrya fluctans	0.08	0.07	0.03	0.03
9	Jamrool		Eugenia malaccensis	0.09	0.079	0.04	0.04
10	Kala-jam	Indian black-berries	Eugenia jambolans	0.28	0.25	0.15	0.16
11	Kalmi-shak		Ipomoea reptans	0.08	0.07	0.06	0.06
12	Kanala-labu*	Orange	Citrus aurantium	0.27	0.24	0.17	0.18
13	Kamrauga	Carambola	Averrhoa carambola	0.13	0.11	0.23	0.23

* The values are given per c.c. of the pulp.

@ Belonging to one particular tree.

TABLE I (Contd.).

Serial No.	Bengali names.	English names.	Scientific names.	Values per g. of fresh food stuff.			
				I ₂ -value (0.01 N).	Ascorbic acid as calculated from iodine values.	Indicator (0.01 M).	Ascorbic acid as calculated from dye values.
14	Kanchalanka (Bombai)	Chillies	<i>Capiscum indicum</i>	0.09 c.c.	0.079 mg.	0.04 c.c.	0.04 mg.
	"	"	"	2.3	2.02	0.43	0.45
	"	"	"	0.34	0.3	0.059	0.1
15	Kanchanug (germinated)	"	<i>Phaseolus mungo</i>	0.15	0.13	0.04	0.04
	"	"	"	0.14	0.12	0.04	0.04
16	Kumra	"	<i>Cucurbita maxima</i>	0.12	0.11	0.05	0.05
17	Kumru-shak	"	Leaves of <i>Cucurbita maxima</i> .	0.27	0.24	0.11	0.11
18	Lau-shak	"	Leaves of <i>Lagenaria vulgaris</i> .	0.14	0.12	0.05	0.05
19	Lebu	Lemon	<i>Citrus medica</i>	0.23	0.2	0.16	0.19
20	Lichoo	Lichi	<i>Nephelium lichi</i>	0.9	0.79	0.46	0.48
21	Nonaphal	Bastard apple	<i>Anona reticulata</i>	0.44	0.39	0.14	0.15
22	Palang-shak	"	<i>Spinach oleracea</i>	0.08	0.07	0.06	0.06
23	Paniphal	"	<i>Tropa. bispinosa</i>	0.2	0.18	0.14	0.15
24	Papaya	Papaw	<i>Carica papaya</i>	0.36	0.32	0.19	0.19
25	Pera	Guava	<i>Psidium gujava</i>	1.67	1.47	1.0	1.04
26	Poin-shak	"	<i>Bassela cordifolia</i>	0.17	0.15	0.08	0.08
27	Sasha	Cucumber	<i>Cucumis sativus</i>	0.06	0.53	0.04	0.04
28	Sobeda	Sapota	<i>Achras sapota</i>	0.03	0.026	0.06	0.06
29	Tal-senab	Core of the unripe fruit of the palm	<i>Borassus flabellifer</i>	0.03	0.07	0.04	0.04
30	Tarmuj	Water-melon	<i>Citrullus vulgaris</i>	0.13	0.11	0.07	0.07
31	Uchehe	"	<i>Momordica Charantia</i>	0.52	0.46	0.32	0.33

TABLE II.

Serial No.	Bengali names.	English names.	Scientific names.	Ascorbic acid (mg.) as calculated from dye values per g. of fresh food-stuff.
1	Pesra	Guava	Psidium guajava	1.04 mg.
2	Am (<i>Langra</i>)	Mango	Mangifera Indica	0.69
3	Lichoo	Lichi	Nephelium lichi	0.48
4	Kancha lanka (Maldah)	Chilli	Capsicum Indicum	0.45
5	Am (<i>Fozli</i>)	Mango	Mangifera Indica	0.34
6	Uchcha	...	Momordica Charantia	0.33
7	Kamranga	Carambola	Averrhoë Carambola	0.23
8	Anarash (Indian variety)	Pine-apple	Ananas Sativa	0.22
9	Lebu	Lemon	Citrus medica	0.19
10	Papaya	Papaw	Carica papaya	0.19
11	Bel (Paka)	Wood-apple	Aegle Marmelos	0.18
12	Kamala-lebu	Orange	Citrus Aurantium	0.18

SUMMARY.

1. Ascorbic acid in the trichloroacetic acid extracts of food-stuffs has been estimated by titration with 2:6-dichlorophenol-indophenol. Glacial acetic acid was introduced to inhibit to some extent the decolorisation by trichloroacetic acid itself.

2. The mango of a particular tree was investigated at the bud, unripe and ripe stages and a progressive decrease in ascorbic acid content was observed. It would seem, therefore, that the process of development of the fruit, unlike that of germination of the seed, involves a progressive disappearance of ascorbic acid.*

3. Of the various Indian food-stuffs investigated, the guava, the mango (*langra* variety) and the lichi appear to be the richest sources of vitamin C. They are richer than the Indian orange and lemon. The different varieties of the mango differ markedly in their ascorbic acid content (*cf.* Guha and Chakravorty, *Indian J. Med. Res.*, 1933, 20, 1045).

4. Germination increases the ascorbic acid content of *mung* 7.8 times, as calculated on the basis of dry weight. There is indication that trichloroacetic acid does not completely extract the vitamin C of germinated *mung*.

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* The same phenomenon has been observed with the guava of a particular tree, investigated at the bud and unripe stages (Guha and Ghosh, *Current Science*, 1934, 3, 201).